

Action of Acetic Anhydride on 2-Acetylresorcin. A New Method for the Synthesis of γ -Resorcylic Acid.

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Though the 4-acyl derivatives of resorcin have been extensively studied the 2-acylresorcins were not known until quite recently. A number of 2-acylresorcins have become easily available since the development of the *Nidhone* Process (Limaye, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 12). The presence of an OH group on either side of the acyl radical makes the compounds amenable to various reactions. The present communication deals with the reaction of acetic anhydride on 2-acetylresorcin, a typical member of the series (Limaye, *loc. cit.*; Limaye and Cangal, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1934, p. 229) which has been prepared from 8-acetyl-4-methylumbelliferone, m.p. 168°. (Limaye, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 375) by the application of the *Nidhone* Process.

On treatment with acetic anhydride alone, the 2-acetylresorcin yields its diacetate (I). When the condensation is carried out in the presence of sodium acetate, however, the reaction takes a different course and three substances have been isolated from the reaction product under conditions described in the experimental part. One of these melts at 122° and has been found to be 2-methyl-3-acetyl-5-hydroxychromone (I). The other substance, m.p. 109°, is the acetate of the chromone mentioned above. The third substance, which appears to be the corresponding coumarin of m.p. 261-62°.

The constitution of the chromone, which will be fully dealt with in a separate communication along with its other properties, is arrived at from its analysis and its easy hydrolysis with alkali which yields acetone, acetic acid, and γ -resorcylic acid. The latter acid was first prepared by Senlofer and Brunner (*Sitzungsber. k. Akad. Wiss. Wien*. 1879, 80, II, 504, 514; *cf.* also Mauthner, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1930, 1, 2881).

The hydrolysis of the 2-methyl-3-acetyl-5-hydroxychromone furnishes an excellent preparative method for γ -resorcylic acid as judged from its purity and yield.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diacetate of 2-acetylresorcin.—The reaction mixture obtained by heating 2-acetylresorcin (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) at 140°-150° for 3 hours was poured into water and extracted with ether. The ether layer was first washed with dilute caustic soda and then with water. The diacetate obtained on evaporating off the ether was distilled at 175°-180°/10 mm. since it decomposes at about 320° under ordinary pressure. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 5.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 61.0; H, 5.1 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-acetyl-5-hydroxychromone.—2-Acetylresorcin (1 g.) was heated with sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) at 160° for 5 hours. The contents of the flask solidified to a brown powder on pouring in excess of water. It crystallises from acetic acid (20 %) in colourless crystals, m.p. 122°, yield 1 g. It is easily soluble in alcohol, benzene and acetic acid and difficultly soluble in water. It is slightly volatile with steam. Its solution in alcohol gives a violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 65.9; H, 4.7. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.6 per cent).

A product melting at 261°-62° was obtained from the acetic acid mother liquor in a very small amount.

The acetyl derivative.—The above chromone was boiled with sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (7 c.c.) at 140°-150° for 3 hours. The product obtained on pouring into water was washed with dilute caustic alkali and then crystallised from boiling water, m.p. 109°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 64.4; H, 4.6. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 64.6; H, 4.6 per cent).

It was also obtained from 2-acetylresorcin directly by using sodium acetate and an excess of acetic anhydride.

Hydrolysis of 2-methyl-3-acetyl-5-hydroxychromone.—The chromone (5.5 g.) was boiled with 50 c.c. of 1N-caustic soda for about 1 hour under a reflux condenser, and the solution distilled, when acetone was identified in the distillate. The residual solution in the flask was then cooled and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and the precipitate dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid. On crystallisation from water (charcoal) the product

melts at 166°-67° (decomp.) with a change at about 110° due to removal of the water of crystallisation. It was identified as γ -resorcylic acid directly and through its derivatives. It gives a blue colouration with ferric chloride solution. When kept over sulphuric acid in vacuum it loses its water of crystallisation. (Found: C, 48.6; H, 4.8; H₂O, 9.7; equiv., 173. C₇H₆O₄·H₂O requires C, 48.8; H, 4.6; H₂O, 10.4 per cent. equiv., 172).

The filtrate containing sulphuric acid was distilled and acetic acid was easily identified in the distillate.

The preparation of γ -resorcylic acid in good yield was effected by boiling 2 methyl-3-acetyl-5-hydroxychromone (1 mol.) with 0.5 N-caustic soda solution (2 mols.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and acidifying the resulting solution with hydrochloric acid when major part of the γ -resorcylic acid was precipitated. A further quantity of the acid was obtained by extracting the filtrate with ether, yield 7.6 g. from 11 g. of the chromone.

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